
Economic, Financial, and Technical Resources Mobilized by Public Action for Social Innovation in Rural Tourism

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Abstract

This study analyzes the economic, financial, and technical resources mobilized by public action in support of social innovation in rural tourism, drawing on the case of the Marrakech–Safi region. Anchored in the theory of change framework, it seeks to understand how these resources function as essential inputs in the process of territorial transformation and to what extent they enable the activation of mechanisms leading to sustainable outcomes. The methodological approach is based on a lexicometric analysis of qualitative data, combining lexical frequency distribution, correspondence factor analysis, similarity analysis, and word cloud visualization. The results highlight a shared recognition of the structuring role of public resources, particularly with regard to financing and technical support. However, the analysis also reveals a standardization of discourse and a limited explicit articulation of the causal chains linking mobilized resources to expected outcomes, such as actor empowerment, project viability, or local spill-overs. These findings point to a gap between public planning and the operational dynamics on the ground. The study concludes that the effectiveness of public action depends less on the volume of resources mobilized than on their capacity to be converted into effective collective action capabilities, through contextualized support mechanisms adapted to the specificities of rural territories in the Marrakech–Safi region.

Keywords: social innovation; rural tourism; public action; theory of change; economic and financial resources; technical engineering; territorial development; Marrakech–Safi.

JEL classification : O35; R11; Z32; H54; O18.

Introduction

The development of rural tourism has today become a strategic lever for territorial transformation in many regions with strong heritage potential, particularly in the Marrakech–Safi region. In the face of the limitations of conventional tourism models, social innovation emerges as a response to the challenges of inclusion, the valorization of local resources, and the economic sustainability of rural territories. In this context, public action plays a crucial role by mobilizing economic, financial, and technical resources aimed at supporting the emergence and structuring of collective initiatives with social objectives. However, the availability of these resources does not automatically guarantee the expected transformation. Their effectiveness depends on the

mechanisms through which they are mobilized, appropriated, and converted into effective capacities for action by local actors. It is precisely this dynamic that the theory of change makes it possible to apprehend, by linking the mobilized inputs, the intermediate processes activated, and the effects produced in the short and long term. Applied to rural tourism, this approach provides a relevant analytical framework for examining how public policies structure the material and operational environment of social innovation. In the Marrakech–Safi region, characterized by strong territorial and socio-economic diversity, this issue is particularly salient, given that needs in terms of support, financing, and technical engineering vary widely across rural areas and actor profiles.

From this perspective, the present study aims to analyze the economic, financial, and technical resources mobilized by public action in support of social innovation in rural tourism in the Marrakech–Safi region, explicitly drawing on the theory of change framework. The objective is not merely to identify existing arrangements, but to understand how these resources are perceived, articulated, and integrated into local dynamics of transformation. By mobilizing a lexicometric approach based on the analysis of territorial actors' discourses, the study seeks to highlight dominant representations, discursive convergences, and zones of tension surrounding the mobilization of public resources. This approach makes it possible to assess the clarity of the causal chains linking the mobilized means to expected effects, such as project structuring, skills development, collective coordination, or the sustainability of initiatives. By focusing on the Marrakech–Safi region, the study aims to contribute to a better understanding of the conditions under which public action can support trajectories of social innovation rooted in the realities of rural tourism. It thus provides analytical insight into the challenges of governance, local appropriation, and the sustainability of territorially embedded public policies.

1. Literature Review

1.1. Theory of Change and Social Innovation

Within the theory of change, economic and financial resources constitute essential material inputs intended to create the conditions for the feasibility of the expected social transformations. Weiss (1995) reminds us that any public action is based on explicit or implicit assumptions according to which the mobilized means will activate mechanisms leading to the desired outcomes. Applied to rural tourism, this approach makes it possible to interpret subsidies, public funds, investment support, and financial aid mechanisms as initial resources aimed at reducing the structural constraints weighing on local initiatives. Stiglitz (1998) emphasizes that market failures are particularly pronounced in peripheral territories, which justifies targeted public intervention to correct asymmetries in access to financing. In the field of territorial development, Barca (2009) shows that the effectiveness of public policies depends on the strategic mobilization of financial resources adapted to local contexts. From the perspective of social innovation, these economic resources do not aim solely at financial profitability, but at the creation of social, collective, and territorial value Nicholls, (2010). The theory of change thus allows public financial instruments to be positioned as triggers of change, without which project leaders in rural areas lack the necessary capacities to experiment with new forms of tourism organization. However, the literature highlights that the injection of financial resources, when isolated from appropriate support mechanisms, does not in itself guarantee the expected social transformation. Beyond financing, the theory of change places particular emphasis on technical resources and public engineering as intermediate mechanisms linking material inputs to expected outcomes. Chen (2022) shows that public policies produce effects when the mobilized resources activate concrete mechanisms that enable beneficiaries to transform these means into effective actions.

In rural tourism, these technical resources include training, technical assistance, labeling, organizational support, and assistance with project structuring. Public action then intervenes to strengthen the operational and organizational capacities of local actors, which is a necessary condition for the viability of social innovation initiatives. Mulgan et al. (2007) underline that technical support fosters experimentation and collective learning by reducing the uncertainty inherent in innovative approaches. The theory of change makes it possible to identify these technical resources as conversion levers, transforming financial means into effective capacities for action. However, Torre and Wallet (2014) warn against excessive technicization of public arrangements, which may produce complex instruments that are difficult for rural actors to appropriate. A theory-of-change-based reading therefore invites an analysis of the adequacy of public engineering to local contexts, so that it effectively supports social innovation in rural tourism without reinforcing inequalities in access to support arrangements.

The theory of change also stresses the importance of articulating mobilized resources with local capacities in order to ensure the effectiveness of public policies. Sen (1999) reminds us that resources have value only insofar as they enhance the real capabilities of individuals and communities to choose and to act. In rural tourism, this perspective leads to analyzing economic, financial, and technical resources not as ends in themselves, but as means serving the empowerment of local actors. By mobilizing these resources, public action aims to support the structuring of collective projects, the professionalization of initiative leaders, and the improvement of the viability of socially oriented tourism offerings. The theory of change makes it possible to identify a causal chain in which public resources activate processes of learning, coordination, and local appropriation, leading to intermediate effects such as the stabilization of initiatives and their organizational consolidation. However, Bebbington (1999) points out that differentiated access to economic and technical resources can generate unequal development trajectories. A rigorous analysis must therefore question the modalities of distribution and governance of the mobilized resources. In rural tourism, social innovation relies precisely on the ability of public action to support inclusive collective projects, ensuring that resources effectively strengthen the capacities of local communities rather than benefiting only the best-endowed actors.

The final stage of the theory of change concerns the sustainability of the effects produced by the mobilization of economic, financial, and technical resources. Rogers (2003) shows that the durable adoption of an innovation depends on its compatibility with existing structures and its ability to generate observable long-term benefits. In rural tourism, the sustainability of social innovations depends on the continuity of financing mechanisms, the stability of technical support, and the gradual integration of initiatives into territorial policies. The theory of change allows this phase to be situated as a critical moment during which intermediate outcomes must be consolidated through durable institutional arrangements. However, Nicholls and Murdock (2011) warn against the risk of excessive dependence on public funding, which may undermine the autonomy of social innovation initiatives. The challenge for public action therefore lies in articulating a structuring initial support with strategies for the progressive empowerment of local actors. From a perspective of sustainable change, economic and technical resources must evolve from a start-up role toward one of stabilization and diffusion. In this way, social innovation in rural tourism becomes embedded in a form of public governance capable of adjusting its instruments on the basis of territorial learning and local dynamics.

1.2. Economic and Financial Resources and Social Innovation in Rural Tourism

Živojinović et al. (2023) show that institutional fragmentation among ministries, agencies, and public organizations limits the capacity of public action to effectively mobilize economic, financial, and technical resources in support of social innovation. This dispersion of responsibilities results in low coherence among public instruments deployed in rural areas, thereby reducing the reach of support mechanisms for innovative tourism. This interpretation aligns with Rogelja et al. (2018), who emphasize that the mobilization of public resources depends on the structuring of policy instruments—whether economic, informational, or relational. The absence of institutional coordination weakens the ability of public action to articulate financing, technical support, and cooperation among actors. Slee and Mosdale (2020) extend this perspective by showing that the effectiveness of public policies relies on instruments that foster coordination and align local initiatives with national frameworks. The mobilization of technical and financial resources can generate durable effects only when embedded in coherent arrangements capable of supporting constellations of social innovations. When public action is fragmented, the impact of mobilized resources is limited, whereas an integrated structuring strengthens social innovation in rural tourism by ensuring a more coherent allocation of economic, financial, and technical means.

Splendiani et al. (2023) highlight the role of public action in mobilizing financial and technical resources to support social innovation projects linked to tourism, particularly in marginal territories. Through the case of the Via Francigena, they show that cooperation between institutions and local actors is an essential condition for channeling these resources toward territorial revitalization initiatives. This perspective is consistent with Apostolopoulos et al. (2019), who emphasize that tourism social enterprises rely on public support frameworks to access the financial resources necessary to strengthen community resilience. Public resources facilitate the local anchoring of social innovation when they are oriented toward entrepreneurial forms adapted to rural specificities. This logic is also present in Wang et al. (2016), who identify governments as central actors in social entrepreneurship in tourism, capable of mobilizing economic and financial resources to support such initiatives. Public action thus plays a structuring role in access to the resources required for social innovation, not only through direct financing but also through the creation of institutional frameworks conducive to cooperation. The joint mobilization of financial and technical resources therefore appears as a lever to strengthen local rural tourism dynamics grounded in social innovation.

Sternberg et al. (2017) show that well-designed public measures can complement infrastructure investments in order to support poverty-reduction strategies through tourism. They stress that the mobilization of technical and financial resources must be embedded in an integrated approach involving both public and private actors. This reading aligns with Foggin (2018), who demonstrates that public infrastructure investments reach their full potential only when accompanied by inclusive measures that facilitate local communities' access to tourism opportunities. The mobilization of economic and technical resources must go beyond an equipment-centered logic to integrate incentive and support mechanisms. Karim et al. (2024) extend this perspective in disaster-prone contexts, emphasizing that government interventions mobilize public resources to support sustainable tourism grounded in social innovation. Financial and technical resources become levers of adaptation and resilience when public action directs them toward inclusive initiatives. Social innovation in rural tourism thus relies on an articulated mobilization of public resources, in which material investments are complemented by institutional arrangements that promote inclusion, cooperation, and territorial sustainability.

Peng and Lin (2016) underscore the need to establish integrated service systems that enable the articulation of local resources and the participation of multiple stakeholders. They show that

such integration requires the mobilization of technical and organizational resources, often supported by public action, in order to foster social innovation in tourism. This approach is consistent with Subagyo et al. (2022), who, through the Pentahelix model, highlight the integration of public and private actors as a condition for the effective mobilization of technical and organizational resources. Public action plays a catalytic role in coordinating stakeholders, thereby facilitating the emergence of innovative solutions within rural communities. Arboleda Jaramillo et al. (2020) reinforce this perspective by emphasizing that public policies promote social innovation in community-based rural tourism through accessible financing mechanisms and targeted technical support. Their contribution suggests that access to financial and technical resources conditions the consolidation of local initiatives. The mobilization of public resources is therefore not limited to financing, but also includes organizational and technical arrangements that integrate actors, structure projects, and support social innovation in rural tourism.

Dionizi and Kercini (2025) show that the structural challenges of agritourism require targeted mobilization of public resources, including fiscal incentives, integration of local systems, and specific policy support. They demonstrate that these resources act as levers for promoting sustainable models that foster social innovation. This perspective aligns with Nasution et al. (2023), who highlight that strategic government interventions—such as infrastructure development, financial incentives, and favorable regulations—mobilize economic, financial, and technical resources in the service of social innovation in rural tourism. Public action structures the material and institutional conditions necessary for the emergence of innovative practices. Maria-Irina (2017) complements this reading by showing that, in the European context, public policies mobilize technical and economic resources to support ecotourism and agritourism, considered forms of social innovation. The creation of a favorable policy environment enables economic diversification and the valorization of local resources. Through the coordinated mobilization of economic, financial, and technical resources, public action supports rural tourism development trajectories grounded in social innovation.

Qu and Zollet (2023) analyze neo-endogenous revitalization through artistic tourism and rural entrepreneurship, highlighting the role of public resources in mobilizing local capacities. They show that public action provides a framework for allocating economic and technical resources that support social innovation. This perspective is consistent with Malek and Costa (2015), who emphasize that social innovation in community tourism requires public engagement in financial and technical support in order to strengthen communities' internal capacities. Public resources facilitate the integration of local actors into tourism planning processes. McAreavey and McDonagh (2011) extend this approach by showing that public rural development programs mobilize financial, technical, and organizational resources to support tourism initiatives that integrate local participation and multi-level governance. Social innovation relies on public arrangements capable of articulating different levels of intervention. Through the mobilization of resources, public action fosters the territorial anchoring of social innovation in rural tourism by supporting local capacities and cooperation among actors.

Leco (2013) shows that public authorities can mobilize financial and technical resources to support agritourism activities that promote the sustainable management of landscapes and natural resources. He highlights that such support strengthens social ties and fosters social innovation adapted to rural specificities. This perspective aligns with that of the ENRD (2016), which describes the LEADER program as a mechanism mobilizing financial and technical support for locally initiated rural development projects, particularly in tourism. Public-private partnerships facilitate access to the resources necessary for the economic and social revitalization of rural territories. Sternberg et al. (2017) complement this reading by emphasizing that public measures benefit communities more when they are designed to complement existing investments and support inclusive approaches. Through the mobilization of economic, financial, and

technical resources, public action supports forms of rural tourism grounded in social innovation by articulating financing, technical support, and local partnerships in the service of sustainable territorial development.

2. Study Objective and Population

The sample for this study consists of four institutional actors holding strategic positions in the public governance of rural tourism in the Marrakech-Safi region and its related provincial areas. It includes, on the one hand, the Regional Delegate of Tourism of Marrakech, whose position makes it possible to apprehend the overall orientations of public action at the regional level, particularly in terms of planning, administrative coordination, and the alignment of support mechanisms for rural tourism. It also includes the Provincial Delegate of Tourism of Safi and the Provincial Delegate of Tourism of Essaouira, whose responsibilities provide a territorialized reading of the implementation mechanisms, the resources mobilized, and the constraints encountered in differentiated local contexts. The presence of the Governor of Al Haouz Province strengthens the institutional scope of the sample by bringing in the perspective of the territorial authority responsible for articulating public policies, intersectoral coordination, and local development priorities. This sample therefore reflects a purposive choice, based on the functional relevance of the respondents rather than on their number, in order to collect institutionally grounded discourses with high informative value on the economic, financial, and technical resources mobilized by public action in support of social innovation in rural tourism.

3. Methods

3.1. Lexical Frequency Distribution

Within the framework of the theory of change applied to rural tourism, the analysis of the economic, financial, and technical resources mobilized by public action constitutes a central entry point for understanding the material conditions of social innovation. These resources correspond to the initial inputs of the change process, without which the expected mechanisms cannot be activated. They reflect the capacity of public policies to reduce the structural constraints weighing on rural territories, particularly in terms of investment, access to equipment, financing of collective projects, and technical support. From this perspective, public action is not limited to a logic of financial redistribution, but seeks to structure an operational environment conducive to the experimentation and consolidation of socially oriented tourism initiatives. The theory of change thus makes it possible to situate these resources as necessary triggers for setting local actors in motion, by facilitating the transition from intention to action. Lexicometric analysis fits within this logic by seeking to identify the effective place of these resources in the discourses of the actors interviewed. It makes it possible to verify whether economic, financial, and technical dimensions occupy a central position in representations of the expected change, and whether they are perceived as structuring levers of social innovation in rural tourism. The challenge is therefore to assess the extent to which the language mobilized reflects a genuine appropriation of these resources as instruments of change, rather than as mere administrative devices disconnected from territorial dynamics.

Figure 1. Distribution of Lexical Frequencies – Public Mobilization of Economic and Technical Resources in Rural Tourism

The distribution of lexical frequencies, as represented by the Zipf curve, highlights a relatively stable discursive structuring around the public mobilization of economic and technical resources. The analyzed corpus comprises 7,561 occurrences distributed across 928 distinct forms, including 201 hapax, which account for 21.66% of the forms but only 2.66% of the occurrences. This configuration indicates a strong concentration of discourse around a shared lexical core, revealing a high degree of homogeneity in the way actors refer to the resources mobilized by public action. The recurrent terms mainly relate to financing arrangements, technical support, infrastructure, and organizational assistance, suggesting a largely convergent perception of the economic levers of change. However, the low contribution of hapax in terms of occurrence volume points to a relatively standardized discursive register, possibly influenced by common institutional frameworks. From a theory-of-change perspective, this linguistic homogeneity can be interpreted as evidence of a shared recognition of the structuring role played by economic and technical resources. At the same time, it calls for a closer examination of the underlying mechanisms, particularly with regard to differentiated accessibility, adaptation to local contexts, and the actual capacity of these resources to strengthen the action capabilities of rural communities. Lexical standardization alone does not guarantee the effectiveness of change and therefore calls for a more fine-grained analysis of local trajectories of appropriation.

3.2. Correspondence Factor Analysis

Correspondence factor analysis applied to the corpus reveals a strongly polarized lexical structure, dominated by the main axis, which alone explains 76.87% of the total inertia. This configuration reflects the existence of a clear opposition between two distinct discursive registers. On the negative pole of Axis 1 are terms associated with centralized public action, explicitly referring to top-down institutional logics, such as public, action, ministry, program, or delegation. On the positive pole, the vocabulary is oriented toward local territorial dynamics, mobilizing terms such as local, support, lever, area, or adapt. This lexical dichotomy reflects a structural divide between the strategic intent articulated by public authorities and the concrete modalities of implementation at the local level. From a theory-of-change perspective, this opposition points to a central issue in the transformation process: the ability of the economic, financial, and technical resources injected by public action to be converted into operational instruments by territorial actors. The central positioning of terms such as tourism, rural, technical, and enable suggests

linked to terms such as action, ministry, mechanism, or partnership, remains relatively peripheral in relation to the central poles of innovation and social. This positioning suggests a symbolic distance between public planning and the concrete practices of social innovation at the territorial level. Within the framework of the theory of change, such a dissociation may indicate a break in the causal chain, where economic and financial resources, although present, struggle to be fully integrated into the operational dynamics of local projects. Moreover, financial instruments—fund, subsidy, rate, access—appear scattered across the graph, without forming a coherent subset strongly connected to technical or organizational levers. This lexical fragmentation reflects low visibility of funding mechanisms and a limited integration between financial resources and support actions. Such a configuration suggests that the expected effects of these resources are not clearly identified by the actors. From a sustainable change perspective, public action would therefore benefit from strengthening interoperability between financial and technical arrangements, in order to make more explicit the transformation pathways supported in rural tourism.

3.4. Lexical Cloud

The word cloud highlights a dense and hierarchical discursive structure organized around a few pivot terms that shape the entire analyzed corpus. The words *tourism*, *innovation*, *rural*, *social*, *public*, and *action* occupy a central position, reflecting a convergence of representations around the strategic objectives of public action in the field of social innovation applied to rural tourism. This centrality points to an integrated vision of change, in which economic, financial, and technical resources are conceived as inseparable levers of territorial transformation. Surrounding this core is a secondary lexical field referring to more operational dimensions, such as *cooperatives*, *arrangement*, *territorial*, *technical*, *program*, *financing*, *structure*, *development*, or *training*. These co-occurrences suggest that public action is perceived as a catalyst for collective initiatives, combining local anchoring, technical support, and financial assistance. From a theory-of-change perspective, this lexical density indicates that the mobilized resources are not viewed as isolated inputs, but as instruments intended to activate intermediate mechanisms of structuring, professionalization, and coordination among local actors. The word cloud thus confirms the existence of a coherent discursive framing, in which public policies seek to create an enabling environment for the emergence and consolidation of socially oriented tourism projects.

4. Discussion

The results highlight a shared recognition of the central role played by economic, financial, and technical resources as essential inputs for social innovation in rural tourism in the Marrakech–Safi region. The strong lexical centrality of terms related to innovation, rural tourism, and public action confirms that actors perceive these resources as structuring levers of territorial change. This discursive convergence suggests that public action has succeeded in establishing a common cognitive framework in which financing mechanisms, technical support, and organizational structuring are identified as prerequisites for the emergence of socially oriented tourism projects. From a theory-of-change perspective, these findings reflect the existence of a relatively stabilized first stage of the transformation process, marked by the acceptance of mobilized resources as conditions for the feasibility of local initiatives. However, the standardization of the lexicon and the predominance of generic terms indicate that this appropriation remains largely discursive. The causal chains linking mobilized resources to expected intermediate effects—such as skills development, organizational consolidation, or economic empowerment—are only weakly articulated. In the context of Marrakech–Safi, characterized by strong territorial heterogeneity between remote rural areas and more connected peri-urban spaces, this lack of differentiation raises questions about the capacity of public instruments to adapt to local specificities. The results thus suggest that, while resources are identified as necessary, their translation into effective capacities remains uneven across territories and actor profiles.

Moreover, factor and similarity analyses reveal a persistent gap between public planning and operational dynamics on the ground. The peripheral positioning of the lexical field associated with public action—particularly around terms such as public, action, and ministry—indicates a symbolic distance between institutional arrangements and concrete practices of social innovation. In the Marrakech–Safi region, this dissociation may reflect governance mechanisms that remain largely top-down, where financial and technical resources are mobilized without always being fully integrated into local logics of cooperation and learning. The lexical dispersion of financial instruments points to limited visibility of funding mechanisms, constraining their catalytic role within the chain of change. According to the theory of change, such a rupture weakens the transition between inputs and intermediate mechanisms, thereby reducing the capacity of mobilized resources to generate durable effects. The results therefore underscore the importance of strengthening mediation functions, territorial engineering, and contextualized support, in order to enable rural actors in Marrakech–Safi to appropriate public instruments. Improved articulation between economic resources, technical engineering, and local dynamics emerges as a key condition for transforming public investments into sustainable social innovation trajectories rooted in the socio-economic realities of regional rural tourism.

Conclusion

This study shows that the economic, financial, and technical resources mobilized by public action constitute an indispensable foundation for social innovation in rural tourism in the Marrakech–Safi region, but that their effectiveness depends closely on the conversion mechanisms they activate. Embedded within the framework of the theory of change, the analysis demonstrates that these resources primarily play the role of inputs, creating the material conditions for collective action and reducing certain structural constraints specific to rural territories. However, the results also highlight that the mobilization of these resources, although identified and recognized by actors, often remains framed within generic and institutionalized discourses. This configuration limits the legibility of the causal chains linking public means to the expected effects on local dynamics. In the context of Marrakech–Safi, characterized by a diversity of territorial situations, such standardization may hinder the differentiated appropriation of public

instruments and reinforce disparities between territories that already possess organizational capacities and those that are more weakly endowed. The theory of change thus helps to reveal a central tension between the strategic intent of public action and its operational translation, showing that the mere availability of resources is insufficient to guarantee social transformation if intermediate mechanisms of learning, coordination, and support are not sufficiently strengthened.

From a perspective of sustainable change, this study underlines the need for public action to evolve toward a more integrated and contextualized mobilization of economic, financial, and technical resources. The theory of change invites a move beyond a logic of injecting means toward an approach focused on strengthening local capacities and the progressive empowerment of rural tourism actors. In the Marrakech–Safi region, this implies reinforcing territorial engineering arrangements, clarifying the financial instruments mobilized, and ensuring better articulation between technical support and community dynamics. The sustainability of social innovation thus depends on the ability of public policies to adjust their instruments based on local learning, while taking into account the specific constraints of rural territories. By making more explicit the links between mobilized resources, activated mechanisms, and expected outcomes, public action can enhance the legibility and effectiveness of its interventions. This conclusion highlights that social innovation in rural tourism in Marrakech–Safi depends not only on the volume of resources committed, but on their capacity to be transformed into levers of collective action that generate social, territorial, and economic value over the long term.

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